

Challenge cards

Tier 1 (Green)

(50,5 x 83,5 mm)

Challenge cards

Tier 3 (Red)

(50,5 x 83,5 mm)

Challenge cards

Tier 2 (Blue)

(50,5 x 83,5 mm)

Bonus cards

(120 x 62 mm)

(127 x 67 mm)

(140 x 77 mm)

Bonus cards

(120 x 62 mm)

(127 x 67 mm)

(140 x 77 mm)

Bonus cards

(120 x 62 mm)

(127 x 67 mm)

(140 x 77 mm)

Penalty cards

(110 x 80 mm)

(110 x 80 mm)

(110 x 80 mm)

Penalty cards

(110 x 80 mm)

(110 x 80 mm)

(110 x 80 mm)

Penalty cards

(110 x 80 mm)

(110 x 80 mm)

(110 x 80 mm)